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**The longicorn beetle tribe Cerambycini Latreille, 1802
(Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Cerambycinae) in the fauna of Asia.
14. A new species of the the genus *Margites* Gahan, 1891
from southern Vietnam**

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Abstract. A new species, *Margites lobanovi* Miroshnikov, **sp. n.**, is described from southern Vietnam. It is very similar to *M. prothemicolis* Jacquot, 2019 from northern Vietnam, but differs by the significantly longer antennae, the more strongly elongate many antennomeres, the somewhat peculiar structure of the pronotum, in particular, the anterior margin being broadly rounded, the presence of a strongly developed shiny median area in the basal part, the slightly shorter elytra, as well as by the structure of the genitalia, namely, the clearly narrower penis uniformly narrowed towards apex in the apical part, its ventral lobe being clearly greater extending beyond apex of the dorsal lobe, the significantly narrower tegmen, the distinctly narrower and more strongly elongate parameres, its apices being more strongly sharpened, the clearly wider tergite 8 being shortly truncate apically.

Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Cerambycini, *Margites*, new species, Vietnam.

**Жуки-дровосеки трибы Cerambycini Latreille, 1802
(Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Cerambycinae) фауны Азии.
14. Новый вид рода *Margites* Gahan, 1891 из Южного Вьетнама**

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Резюме. Описан новый вид *Margites lobanovi* Miroshnikov, **sp. n.** из Южного Вьетнама. Он очень сходен с *M. prothemicolis* Jacquot, 2019 из Северного Вьетнама, но отличается значительно более длинными усиками с более вытянутыми многими члениками, своеобразной скульптурой диска переднеспинки, в том числе наличием сильно развитого продольного гладкого блестящего срединного участка (мозоли), формой переднего края переднеспинки, слегка более короткими надкрыльями и строением гениталий.

Ключевые слова: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Cerambycini, *Margites*, новый вид, Вьетнам.

Until now, fourteen Asian species of the genus *Margites* Gahan, 1891 have been known, two of which were described just recently [Miroshnikov, 2018; Jacquot, 2019].

This paper further one species of the genus stemming from southern Vietnam is described.

The material treated here belongs to the following private collections:

cAM – collection of Alexandr Miroshnikov (Krasnodar, Russia);

cPJ – collection of Philippe Jacquot (Montboucher-sur-Jabron, France).

Margites lobanovi Miroshnikov, **sp. n.**
(Figs 1, 3, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (cAM) (Fig. 1): S Vietnam, Binh Thuan Prov., Dong Tien, ~11°17'N / 108°00'E, 05.2019 (local collector).

Comparative material. *Margites prothemicolis* Jacquot, 2019: 1♂, holotype (cPJ) (photographs; Figs 2, 4, 7, 9, 11), N Vietnam, Ninh Binh, Dong Tam, Cuc Phuong National Park, 90 m, 20°15'N / 105°43'E, 3.05.2019 (leg. D. Spiridonov).

Diagnosis. Based on male characters, this new species is very similar to *M. prothemicolis* Jacquot, 2019, but differs

by the significantly longer antennae (despite the fact that the body length is only slightly larger than that of the latter species), the more strongly elongate many antennomeres, as in Fig. 1 (cf. Fig. 2), the somewhat peculiar structure of the pronotum, in particular, the anterior margin being broadly rounded, as in Fig. 6 (in *M. prothemicolis*, the anterior margin is obtuse-angled in the middle part, as in Fig. 7), the presence of a strongly developed shiny median area in the basal part, as in Fig. 6, the slightly shorter elytra, as well as by the structure of the genitalia, namely, the clearly narrower penis uniformly narrowed towards apex in the apical part, as in Fig. 10 (cf. Fig. 11), its ventral lobe being clearly greater extending beyond apex of the dorsal lobe, as in Fig. 10 (cf. Fig. 11), the significantly narrower tegmen, as in Fig. 8 (cf. Fig. 9), the distinctly narrower and more strongly elongate parameres, its apices being more strongly sharpened, as in Fig. 8 (cf. Fig. 9), the clearly wider tergite 8 being shortly truncate apically, as in Fig. 3 (cf. Fig. 4).

Description. Male. Body length 12.4 mm, humeral width 3 mm. Body mainly brown-black; eyes and part of mandibles black; antennae, trochanters, tibiae, tarsi, very apex of pronotum, part of

head ventrally, prosternal process apically and most of mandibles reddish brown and red-brown tones; femora dark brown.

Head with a very gentle median groove between upper lobes of eyes; antennal tubercles well-expressed, but weakly convex and drawn mainly backward and laterad; eyes moderately convex, as in Fig. 5; submentum with rough transverse folds; genae relatively short; antennae unusually long, slightly more than twice as long as body (in male of *M. prothemicolis*, antennae only about 1.6 times as long as body); length ratio of antennomeres 1–11, 28 : 7 : 40 : 34 : 59 : 60 : 58 : 56 : 55 : 54 : 70; antennomere 1 with a very dense and confluent, partly rugose puncturation; antennomere 2 barely longitudinal.

Pronotum distinctly longitudinal, 1.09 times as long as wide; base 1.1 times as wide as apex; disc flat, with a scabrous sculpture similar to *M. prothemicolis*, but unlike the latter (Fig. 7), in basal part with a very well-expressed, longitudinal, smooth, shiny, median area, partly being sparsely punctured, as in Fig. 6.

Scutellum triangular, strongly narrowed towards apex, sharpened apically.

Elytra nearly parallel-sided, 2.5 times as long as humeral width; with a small, very dense and confluent puncturation; apical external angle obtuse-angled, but well-expressed, sutural angle distinctly rounded.

Prosternum with a distinct transverse groove in front of middle, with irregular, partly transverse folds; prosternal process without apical tubercle; mesosternal process between coxae about twice as wide as prosternal process (Fig. 5), without tubercle dorsally; metasternum and sternites with a small dense puncturation; metasternum with a distinct median suture; last (visible) sternite subtruncate apically; last (visible) tergite widely rounded at apex, as in Fig. 12.

Legs moderately long; meso- and metatibiae with a gentle, but distinct longitudinal carina on sides; metatarsomere 1 subequal to metatarsomeres 2 and 3 combined.

Recumbent setation silvery greyish, relatively uniform on elytra, but on pronotum forming a somewhat peculiar pattern, as

in Fig. 6; more or less long, erect, light setae mainly developed on pronotum and apex of abdomen.

Genitalia as in Figs 3, 8, 10.

Note. The antennae of the new species are the longest among all congeners.

Distribution. Southern Vietnam.

Etymology. This new species is dedicated to the memory of Andrei Lvovich Lobanov (1940–2020), a famous Russian coleopterologist who was the creator and permanent web editor of the grandiose and unique site “Beetles (Coleoptera) and coleopterists” (<http://zin.ru/Animalia/Coleoptera/rus/index.html>).

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Figs 1–4. Species of the genus *Margites* Gahan, 1891, habitus and details of structure. 1, 3 – *M. lobanovi* sp. n., male, holotype; 2, 4 – *M. prothemicolis* Jacquot, 2019, male, holotype (photographs by Philippe Jacquot); 3–4 – tergite 8, dorsal view.

Рис. 1–4. Виды рода *Margites* Gahan, 1891, общий вид и детали строения.

1, 3 – *M. lobanovi* sp. n., самец, голотип; 2, 4 – *M. prothemicolis* Jacquot, 2019, самец, голотип (фотографии Ф. Жако); 3–4 – 8-й тергит сверху.

Figs 5–12. Species of the genus *Margites* Gahan, 1891, males, holotypes, details of structure.
 5–6, 8, 10, 12 – *M. lobanovi* sp. n.; 7, 9, 11 – *M. prothemicolis* Jacquot, 2019 (photographs by Philippe Jacquot). 5 – head, ventral view, and pro- and mesosterna; 6–7 – pronotum; 8–9 – tegmen, ventral view; 10–11 – apical part of penis, ventral view; 12 – last (visible) tergite (without the very base), dorsal view.

Рис. 5–12. Виды рода *Margites* Gahan, 1891, самцы, голотипы, детали строения.
 5–6, 8, 10, 12 – *M. lobanovi* sp. n.; 7, 9, 11 – *M. prothemicolis* Жако, 2019 (фотографии Ф. Жако). 5 – голова снизу, про- и мезостернум; 6–7 – переднеспинка; 8–9 – тегмен снизу; 10–11 – верхняя часть пениса снизу; 12 – последний (видимый) тергит (без самого основания) сверху.